

MODELING SLOPE AND ASPECT INFLUENCE ON LANDSCAPE MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGE IN NDELE, RIVERS: A GIS-BASED ASSESSMENT

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Abstract:

This study examines the complex relationships between slope, aspect, and landscape evolution. The study analyzed how slope and aspect as fundamental topographic factors significantly influence landscape evolution. The primary data was derived from extraction of DEM resolution 30m×30m LANDSAT TM⁻ imagery downloaded from United State Geological Survey. The secondary data were gotten from simulation results carried out with digital elevation model (DEM) using Landscape Process Modeling at Multi dimensions and Scales (LAPSUS); a GIS-based Landscape Evolution Model. The findings of the study showed that the interaction between slope and aspect shaped Ndele landscape through influencing erosion patterns, landform morphology, and ecosystem dynamics. Slope angle controls erosion rates as shown that steeper slopes occur in the Northern regions of Ndele while lower, gentler slope are continually worn down with the lowest value occurring in 2016 at 40.05. Conclusively, the study findings infer that there is an inverse relationship between slope angle and soil erosion which led to structural change in the areas landscape.

Keywords: GIS, Geomorphometry, Geomorphology, Modelling, Terrain

1. INTRODUCTION

Slope and aspect significantly influence landscape change and evolution through various geological and geomorphologic processes. Topographical influence on landforms and soils may occur as a result of the combined effects of topographic variables such as slope aspect, water erosion and deposition etc. A land surface's slope is a measurement of its inclination or steepness. According to Muleta, Kidane, and Bezie (2021), there are three ways to characterize it: steep slopes, which are sharp inclines that are frequently prone to erosion or landslides; gentle slopes, which are gradual inclines that are frequently more stable and appropriate for a variety of land uses; and uniform slopes, which are a constant incline over a specific area. The

measurement of slope can be done through analyzing the angle of slope i.e. the angle between the slope and the horizontal plane which is measured in degrees; or through measuring the slope Gradient which is the ratio of vertical to horizontal distance. Aspect refers to the direction in which a slope or land surface faces. It is an important factor in determining various environmental and ecological conditions. The importance of aspect is evident in the following ways: Aspect affects the amount of solar radiation received, influencing temperature and microclimate. Aspect influences the type and density of vegetation, with some species preferring specific orientations and also, Aspect affects soil moisture levels, with some areas receiving more shade or sunlight.

Landscape morphological change refers to the alteration of the shape, form, and structure of the landscape over time. Landforms are unavoidably, constantly acted upon by surficial processes and with the expiration/transition of time; the operation of the process would usually leave a clear and decipherable trail on the landform (Umeuduji, 2010). It is now well known that while the processes and activities that shape and evolve landscapes are dynamic in both place and time, the laws that govern them remain constant (Wassie, 2020).

The process of creating a model—a typical representation of a system—is referred to as modeling. Simulation modeling is the process of simulating or imitating how a real-world system appears over a specified length of time using a computerized quantitative model (Deche, 2023). When building an actual system, simulation is utilized to explain how the system responds (Abebe et al., 2022). Landscape Evolution Models (LEMs) refer to quantitative tools utilized to replicate and reproduce land surface processes and landscape evolution (Baas, 2007). In landscape evolution modeling, landscapes are represented in digital format and the rates of the different processes forming the landscapes are calculated and used to depict the changes. The most common digital representation of the landscape is a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). A Digital Elevation Model, (DEM), is a gridded arrangement of longitude, latitude and elevation (x, y and z) of diverse resolutions of the area under study in a raster format (Coulthard, Macklin and Kirkby, 2002),

Slope evolution theories upon which the foundational basis of landscape evolution is drawn from includes- the theory of Peneplanation, Pede-planation, Etch-planation etc. Although most of these theories no longer dominate in research, they are still employed as

teaching tools. The work of Grove Karl Gilbert can be assumed to have the most lasting strong influence on modern and process geomorphology (Yochelson, 1980). Gilbert put up the idea that slopes form as a result of the progressive deep weathering of rocks by aggressive and vigorous denudation agents, which causes rock breakdown and decay. The work of American physical geographer William Morris Davis was the first model of landscape evolution to be extensively accepted and well received within the field of geomorphology. According to Davis' cycle of erosion for a broad-scale landscape evolution, there are four main, gradual stages of landscape evolution. The first is a river-dominated stage of erosion that results from the impulsive uplift of the land surface above base level, which sculpts deep, narrow valleys. The second stage is characterized by river incision, which shapes the appearance of the landscape. Slope decline is a phenomenon that is introduced in the third stage, which is the mature landscape. Here, hillslopes take on a concavo-convex shape as the mean height and mean relief gradually drop. Lastly, the long-term action of erosion through hillslope creep lowers all landscapes into a lowland or rolling, undulating plain in stage 4, the penultimate stage. In his "old age" stage of landscape evolution, which signified the end of the geographic cycle, Davis dubbed the resulting low-lying erosion surface the "penultimate plain," or peneplain (from the Latin word pene, almost).

Presently, various literatures exist which gives a valid explanation on why steep slopes wear down at slow rates gradually. Slope length, direction and curvature play an essential function in soil formation. Thus, topography is considered an important variable in soil formation. In a set of circumstances of all these events, to gain a greater knowledge and understanding on the

influence of slope and aspect on the landscapes in Ndele, basic research questions arose such as: How does slope influence landscape morphology?

2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research is to assess how slope and aspect influence landscape morphological change using GIS techniques in Ndele, Rivers. The primary objectives of this research are to:

1. Determine how slope and aspect interact to steer topography
2. Quantify the impact of slope on erosion rate.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Ndele, Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Ndele is located in the South East Senatorial district of Rivers State. Ndele lies on lat. $6^{\circ} 43' 30''\text{N}$ and lat. $6^{\circ} 54' 0''\text{E}$; long. $4^{\circ} 50' 0''\text{N}$ and $5^{\circ} 10' 0''\text{N}$. It is bounded by Elele-Alimini in the North, Degema in the South, Odegu in the East; Rumuekpe in the West. (www.rivers.gov.ng/portal). A map of the study area is shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Emohua LGA showing the study area; insert Rivers state, Nigeria. Source: OSGOF 2011 Nigeria Shapefile.

Climate and Vegetation

Rainfall in Ndele is bimodal (i.e. having to modes/peaks) with the wettest months in June and September. Ndele is a heavy rainfall region with about 2000mm - 2500mm per annum rainfall, mean annual temperature range between

23° - 32°C and a mean relative humidity of over 80% per annum.

In terms of vegetation, Ndele has luxuriant and affluent eco-systems which is characterized by diversified flora and fauna utilized profitably due to sufficient rainfall and favorable weather

conditions. Ndele was originally a rainforest region which has been modified by anthropogenic activities. Economic trees, particularly oil palm, are in abundance thus; shrubs and palms occur on the sandy ridges upland while mangrove species occur in the water zones and swamps (www.rivers.gov.ng/portal).

Geology and Soil

The land surface is predominantly the coastal sand ridge zone which is generally less than 20m above sea level (www.onlinenigeria.com). The topography of Ndele is mainly characterized by effluents, creeks and swamps which crisscross the low-lying plains in varying dimensions.

The soils are mostly sandy loams. They are organic in nature, essentially sandy in texture and supports agriculture extensively. The mean soil pH value in the mangrove forest of the area is 3.60 while the freshwater swamp forest and the lowland rain forest have mean soil pH values of 4.50 and 5.20 respectively (www.rivers.gov.ng/portal).

3.2 Methods of Data Collection

The various tools which were employed to model landscape morphological change includes: field survey, topographic maps, GIS and Remote

Sensing software, ArcGIS and a modeling software, LAPSUS (Landscape Process modeling at Multi dimensions and Scales) based on the early works of Kirkby (1971; 1978; 1986) and Foster and Meyer (1972; 1975).

LAPSUS model (Landscape Modeling at Multi-dimensions and Scales) is a multi-process landscape model developed by Jeroen Schoorl (Schoorl et al., 2000; Schoorl and Veldkamp, 2001; Schoorl, Veldkamp and Bouma, 2002) to model soil redistribution spatially at explicit annual time-step.

In LAPSUS, each process has parameters which can be used to analyze it and these parameters are controlled by a user interface. The LAPSUS model requires seven indices as its Input parameters namely: DEM (unfiltered, saved in ASCII format), soil depth, land use classes, tillage field, mean annual rainfall, mean annual infiltration and mean annual evaporation. These parameters which will be used as default constant values are to be employed by selecting/checking the f(x, y) box in the input tab shown (in figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: LAPSUS input tab showing the required parameters and their constant values. Source: LAPSUS user Guide (v0.97), Model version 5.0.

Map outputs for each of the [x] time steps were run annually and saved as map image by the model. These output maps were then imported, digitized and overlaid using ArcGIS 10.4.1 (ESRI, US) to explain landscape evolution at discrete temporal time-step extent/interval of four years, 10⁴ years (1986, 1996, 2006 and 2016), thus achieving the first research objective.

The output maps were visually presented and evaluated using ArcGIS 10.4.1 (ESRI, US).

4. RESULTS

Patterns of Ndele landscape were simulated using annual time steps and the resultant effects are visualized for all the scenarios as simulation results to detect and present evidence of transformations in Ndele.

4.1 LAPSUS simulation results. Slope and Aspect of Ndele landscape, 10⁴ years.

Figure 4.1a: Slope of Ndele for the four years (1986, 1996, 2006 and 2016).

Figure 4.1b: Aspect of Ndele for the four years (1986, 1996, 2006 and 2016).

Changes in elevation of Ndele’s topography areas DEM for the four years. The values derived were derived from surface analysis of the study areas DEM for the four years. The values derived are shown (in table 4.1)

Table 4.1: changes in elevation values derived from surface analysis, Ndele DEM 10⁴.

Year	spatial analysis, surface terrain parameters		
	Slope (°)	Aspect (N' S')	Curvature

	Highest		Lowest		Highest		Lowest	
1986	89.96	35.63	min>0.0027	SE	223		-7.13	
			max>359.63	N				
1996	89.34	63.23	min>0.073	SE	101		-919	
			max>359.97	N				
2006	89.94	66.23	min>0.081	SE	750		-593	
			max>359.91	N				
2016	89.96	40.05	min>0.0132	SE	773		-735	
			max>359.99	N				

N- North, SE-South east, min- minimum/lowest, max-maximum/highest
Source: Field data, 2019.

4.2 LAPSUS Graph output results.

LAPSUS produced cross-sectional profile graphs of the simulated process for each timestep/year as shown in figure 4.1.2 (i-iv).

Figure 4.2: Cross-sectional profile graph, Ndele for the four years (1986, 1996, 2006 and 2016).

5. DISCUSSIONS.

The research objective of determining how slope and aspect interact to steer topography was achieved through examining possible scenarios of land structure change in the study area. The interaction of erosion, uplift and various changes in topography has in further ways shaped the landscape, beginning from the undulating plain form to alluvial fans and to river terraces in the landscape (refer to study area in-text morphology, geology; page 7). As shown in figure 4.14a and b, landscape elevation and relief changed within the space of 40 years (i.e. 1986 – 2016, 10^4 years). Highest height of Ndele in meters was represented by the contour and spot height of 70m class topography with the lowest occurring at 10m while in 2016, the landscape

height and structure declined with the highest contour and spot height recorded at 50m class while its lowest is <10. The DTM outputs simulation for scenario II tectonics in fig 4.2 shows a declining trend from 1986 till 2006 with changes from 34.57 – 27.78; and a surprising uplift/stability in 2016 as it becomes higher in elevation value of 31.88 for high areas in Ndele. However lower areas continually decreased in topography occurring between 0.025 – 0.002. An analysis of the LAPSUS results showed that the lowest value among the slopes was obtained to be 8% slope, while the highest values in terms of LnE/LnS had 18% slope value. Land use change can create deviation and change in land structure when studying landscape development either positively or negatively. This suggests that

a link exist between the spatial-temporal simulation and resolution of landscape evolution and the presently existing natural landscape.

To investigate how slope angle and aspect influenced erosion rates in Ndele environments, the slope tool calculated the maximum change in elevation rate from one cell to its neighbors, indicating the level of steepness of Ndele terrain. The slope values show higher levels of variability. Slope variations which are presented in table 4.6 shows that steeper slopes occur in the Northern regions of Ndele and they are resistant to erosion and weathering while lower, gentler slope are continually worn down in the Sothern regions with the lowest value occurring in 2016 at 40.05. The steeper slopes are more prone to erosion and sediment transport with increased erosion rates. Furthermore, the study highlighted the higher predominance of depressions in flat areas than high-relief landscape. Curvature was calculated from the slope form derivative in order to analyze if any given part of Ndele surface is convex or concave. The Curvature tool has different options in its computation and its two major types include Plan and Profile Curvature. These were employed in primarily explaining terrain effects on water erosion and water flow. For curvature, 1996 had higher values than 1986 for Weighted Shape; and 2016 had higher values than 2006 for Weighted Shape. These changes occurred mainly because Ndele curvature has a convex surface, and also the area is generally exposed and drain to other areas. Slope angle and curvature affected soil formation, thickness, and stability in the area. The profile curvature infers that Ndele has accelerated flows, which influences deposition and erosion. The increase in slope height due to erosion affects soil depth and species diversity (Tekle and Maryo, 2022). Soil surface is exposed and left unprotected against erosion, thus

reducing its storage capacity through shortened plant root mass (Godwin and Ayadiuno, 2020). This shows the inverse relationship between slope angle, soil coverage and soil erosion. Also, slopes influence the amount and distribution of precipitation and these are needed for plant growth (Mengist and Soromessa, 2021). The Aspect tool calculated the direction slope plane faces for each of the cell in the 10^4 years under study. The slope aspect of a surface determines sunlight amount and solar radiation it receives. Results from aspects shows Ndele have a northerly aspect. North-facing slopes receive less direct sunlight, often cooler and are more shaded. This explains why the study area is wet and cold.

Conclusion.

Conclusively, this research on landscape evolution modeling in Ndele contributed to knowledge by aiding in the verification of the fact that landscape evolution theories and hypothesis; through combining all the relevant landscape forming processes results into a pertinent digital landscape data can be employed in analyzing topographical changes with time. The results derived in landscape evolution modeling and its coalition with fieldwork in this study has demonstrated that landscape evolution models can fully be used to simulate actual landscape evolution on timescales of 10^4 years. Analysis of Ndele as a region with a smaller spatial extent portrayed that the use of LEMs to simulate the response of landscape to change in tectonics, has the potential to heighten researchers' interest in studying landscape dynamics and tectonics effects for smaller catchment areas. In general, the results derived from these DEM scenarios indicates the relationship which exists between geomorphic processes and landscape dynamics and understanding the relationship nature, extent and

severity is of paramount importance in geomorphometry.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All data used in this research can be made available upon reasonable request.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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